

Key Retail Store Attributes Determining Consumers' Perceptions: An Empirical Study of Consumers of Retail Stores Located in Ahmedabad (Gujarat)

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Abstract

In the recent times, India has witnessed transformation in the shopping habits of the consumers. Modern retail outlets have provided Indian consumers with new shopping exposure and constantly evolving choice for shopping with embracing on wide range of products. Modern retail formats are operating in different sizes and shapes. They are quite different in terms of the ownership, the kind of premises (format) used, and the orientation of the product range. This study examines empirically how consumers' perceptions towards stores get affected by demographic, situational and store variables when they make purchase decision.

The study emphasizes that product range, store layout, shopping convenience; promotional schemes, product pricing, customer service, employee behavior, and store ambience significantly influence the customers. Moreover, the paper provides crucial insights to people in organized

retail business by identifying important variable like 1) Courteous Staff Members, 2) Customer Attention, 3) Offers and Discounts, 4) Comfort and Elegance, 5) Proximity, 6) Variety, 7) Speedy Service, 8) Assurance that must be considered while designing their operations.

Keywords: Retailing, Consumers, Perceptions, Store Attributes

Introduction

The recent time has been observed as growth of Indian organized retail market with many folds. Numerous business groups are attracted in the past few years, including some renowned business groups like Bharti, Future, Reliance, and Aditya Birla to establish hold, showing the future growth in times to come. It is predicted by the Industry estimates that the retail sector in India is expected to touch US\$637 billion by 2015 with the organized segment expected to account for 22 per cent, up

from the present four per cent. In addition, organized retail sector has also grabbed the attention of foreign companies, showing their interest to enter India. In India, the organized retail market will touch roughly US\$30 billion by the year end of 2010. In India, the modern retail formats are operating in different sizes and shapes. They are quite different in terms of the ownership of the retail business, the kind of premises (format) used, and the orientation of the product range. Modern retail outlets have provided consumers with new shopping exposure and constantly evolving choice for shopping with embracing on wide range of portfolio.

It is known that retailing is a process of selling goods and services to the final consumers for their personal, or their family's consumption. Hence, it is very essential for the retailers to acquire as much as information and understanding about the consumers. This make them well-informed and familiar about consumers on diverse fronts like their demographics, psychographics and socio-economic status, identifying the right consumer base that will prove to be significant for retailers.

There are many past studies that focus on the consumer behavior and have helped in understanding about the consumers. As it is known that consumer behavior is ever evolving field of study, this is an attempt to understand consumers' perceptions, attitudes and buying behavior. On the basis of literature reviewed on consumers in retailing, it was identified that knowing ever changing consumers is very significant for the retailers. Hence this research could be beneficial to researchers, retailers,

management consultants, business people, academicians, trainers, and shoppers.

Review of Literature

The consumers are always found with distinct needs and wants which may be because of their consumption pattern, demographics (like age profile, working patterns, income and expenditure, occupation), lifestyle changes, buying process, shopping behavior, shopping motivations and objectives, and changing consumer etc. In the same regard Abercrombie et. al., (1994) mentioned that the happening consumption culture is contemporary therefore the evolving scenario of the consumption pattern over a period of time propels retailers to spotlight on consumers' perceptions, attitudes, and buying behavior.

The consumers' profile apprehension explains consumers' transformations over time and constructs predictions about how the consumption pattern will evolve in the coming time. For instance, the predictions given by India's National Council for Applied Economic Research reveals about 17 million households – 90 million people – with annual earnings ranging between \$4,500 and \$22,000 comprise middle class population currently in India. Moreover, 287 million were identified as 'aspirers' or in the near future these consumers are expected to join the middle class. Further it is expected that these groups will spend more on advancing and varying their lifestyles and eating habits like, using processed and convenience items.

It was realized that there are other reasons than the need to buy the simple physical goods by Tauber (1972) in his research

‘why do people shop? He further stressed that, there are various motivations for shopping influenced by several factors, many of them are related to personal and social motivations of consumers and a few of them are associated to the buying of products. It is therefore necessary for retailers to research and understand what makes shoppers highly satisfied. In addition to this, several consumer researches have revealed other psychological motivations for shopping.

Understanding consumer behavior is incomplete until describing how consumers make choices, as clarified by Foxall & Goldsmith (1994) in their book on Consumer Psychology for Marketing. Consumers come to know and learn about brands through various communication vehicles like, packages, promotions, advertisements, business talks and word of mouth. After consumers become aware about the brands, their buying decisions are guided by the perceptions or impressions of the brands that they have formed from the information. Therefore, the study of consumer perception is an element of largely unconscious processes of consumer behavior.

Because consumers make decisions and take actions based on what they perceive as reality, it is essential to describe the term perception and the related concepts that influence the consumers to buy. Schiffman & Kanuk (2007) described perception as, “the process by which an individual selects, organizes, and interprets stimuli into a meaningful and coherent picture of the world.” In the simplest term Young (1961) defined “to perceive is to observe

through the senses.” It is right that some of the writers have presented perception in terms of five senses. As Foxall & Goldsmith (1994) mentioned in their book that consumers become aware about the environment through the five senses and therefore sensation is the process with which perception begins. But perception is not synonymous with sensation despite their clear interconnectedness.

To Perceive = {to see, to hear, to touch, to taste, to smell, to sense - internally}
{some} {thing, event, relation}

Consumer perception is an approximation of reality. Consumer mind tries to make sense out of the stimuli to which they are exposed. Perception is the way in which an individual interprets stimuli received by the senses. Perception is defined as, “A process through which consumers make sense out of the world” by Runyon (1977). In a broad sense, Wilkie W. L., (1986) mentioned that the topic of perception is concerned with the translation from the external, physical world to the internal, mental world that each of us actually experiences.

The study carried out by Sinha & Banerjee (2004) attempted to know the determinants of retail store selection based on the perception of consumers on visiting various types of stores, their observations on the levels of various service and physical parameters related to the store visited. There are three basic functions that are contained in the definition of perception: sensing a stimulus in the external world; selecting and attending to certain stimuli and not others; and interpreting the stimuli and giving them meaning.

Joyce & Lambert (1996) have expressed that evaluation done by individuals of store image could be affected by self-views developed by them (e.g. type of store shopped, personnel employed, music and videos played, other aesthetic store dimensions). It lies at the heart of the manner in which he responds to his world. Foxall & Goldsmith (1994) support that the effective management of marketing activities of an organization rest on the following two fundamentals:

- First, consumers act on their perceptions which basically come from the information that they receive.
- Second, managers need to understand the nature of perceptions of their consumers and potential consumers have of themselves, their social world, and products available to them.

The study carried out by Joyce & Lambert (1996) has depicted that consumers' perceptions regarding the store image are likely to be affected by the types of stores consumers repeated visited in the past and the attributes associated with those stores (e.g. color, lighting, signage, clientele, salespeople).

According to O'Connor (1990), the primary factual elements or attributes determining a retailer's image by forming consumers perceptions, include price, variety, assortment within product categories, quality, products, service (or lack thereof) and location. Type of customer, shop location, price levels, service offered, merchandise mix, advertising and the characteristics of the physical facilities are listed by Terblanche (1998) as some

of the factors determining store related perceptions. Similarly, Peter and Olson (1990) observed that the most commonly studied store image dimensions are merchandise, service, clientele, physical facilities, promotion, convenience and store atmosphere, which closely resemble Lindquist's proposed dimensions. Sheth and Mittal (2004) stated that: "Store image, the sum total of perceptions customers have about a store, is determined by these merchandise, service, and price factors; it is also determined by atmospherics, advertising, and store personnel." However, as with the definition of store image, no consensus has been reached on a set of universal store image dimensions.

For the purpose of this study, Lindquist's framework of store image was selected as a viable point of departure for identifying store image dimensions and descriptions (incorporating the relevant attributes for each dimension), since it proves to be the most comprehensive in store image literature. Cognitive, affective and physical components of store image are included in the proposed store image attribute dimensions. Therefore, in building on the foundation established by Lindquist (1974,1975), as well as taking into account what other researchers have identified, the following store image dimensions that are mostly forming and influencing consumers' perceptions are also considered for the study (Refer Table 1). Thus modern retailers need to examine perceptions of consumers about important aspects of organized retail stores.

Table: 1 Consumers' Perception Dimension of the Retail Store

Perception Dimension	Description of Dimension (Attributes)	References
Merchandise	Quality, selection or assortment, styling or fashion, guarantees, pricing.	James et al..1976 O'connor,1990 Terblanche, 1998 Peter & olson,1990
Service	Service general, sales clerk service, Self service, ease of merchandise return, delivery service, credit policies of store.	James et al..1976 O'connor,1990 Terblanche,1998 Peter & olson,1990
Clientele	Social class appeal, self image congruency, store personnel.	Martineau, 1958 James et al..1976 Terblanche,1998 Peter & olson,1990
Physical facilities	Elevators, lighting, air conditioning, washroom, store layout, aisle placement and width carpeting, architecture.	Martineau,1958 Terblanche,1998 Peter & olson,1990
Convenience	Convenience general, location Convenience, parking.	O'connor,1990 Peter & olson,1990
Promotion	Sales - Promotions, advertising, displays, trading stamps, symbols, colours.	Martineau,1958 Terblanche,1998 Peter & olson,1990
Store atmosphere	Atmosphere congeniality	James et al..1976 Peter & olson,1990

Objectives of the Research Study

The main objective of the research was to study and understand consumers' perceptions towards organized retail stores and the relationship between the demographic variables and consumers' perceptions. Now, in the land of shopkeepers, shopping experience is changing rapidly. The retail landscape is not only significantly developing in metros but also in the small cities. The increasing number of organized retail stores in India has offered new shopping experience to consumers. This study was an effort to examine the magnitude of perception towards retail stores. The main objectives covered under this research were as follows:

1. To measure the relationship between the demographic variables and consumers' perceptions towards organized retail stores.
2. To identify the popular factors contributing in framing consumers' perceptions.
3. To suggest how consumers' perceptions affect their shopping.
4. To bring out the areas of improvements in retail stores and to suggest competent and innovative strategies for retail stores.

Research Methodology

For this study, an exploratory research design was considered appropriate. The information was collected through a sample survey. Data were collected from the consumers visiting Big Bazaar, D-Mart, Reliance Mart, and Vishal Mega Mart in Ahmedabad (Gujarat state). Researchers have drawn the samples applying convenience sampling procedure. The sample size was determined applying proportions (determining the sample size when estimating proportions). Considering confidence level of 95 per cent, a margin of sampling error (or precision) of ± 5 per cent, and proportion of a sample for the survey is shown in the following table. Thus, the final sample size was calculated to be 196. Thus, the study attempted to attain sample reliability within ± 5 per cent margin of error at the 95 per cent confidence level.

Table: 2 Determination of Sample Size

City	pa	qb	p*q	SSEc	Std. Value	p*q/SSE	Sample Size (n)
Ahmedabad	0.85	0.15	0.128	0.0025	3.8416	0.000650771	196
a. Probability , b. 1 - Probability, c. Square of Sampling Error							

The secondary data was collected from journals, magazines, reports, research studies, government publications, professional publications, research organizations and websites.

A survey approach was chosen in order to collect data directly from consumers visiting the identified organized retail stores operating in the city of Ahmedabad. A survey methodology permits the use of questions to measure constructs exclusively internal to respondents, e.g. perceptions, attitudes, opinions, intentions, etc., (Cooper and Schindler, 1998), and the answers can be collected and combined to represent the answers of an entire population (Reaves, 1992). At an exit door (store intercept manner) was conducted at storefront with consumers who were asked to fill the questionnaire, used by Rani and Velayudhan (2008) in their study.

For the purpose of computing statistical accuracy researchers applied one sample T-test, Chi-square test, Binomial test, Factor Analysis, Cross-tabulation, and Percentage & Frequency Analysis. From the calculated outcomes meaningful interpretations were drawn for the organized retail sector in Ahmedabad city

Data Analysis and Results

Here given table (Table: 3) shows the summary of the demographics of the samples selected for the study. From the summary, it is clear that 78% of the respondents fall in the age group of 18 to 34 years and around 73% of the respondents surveyed were graduates. Almost half of the consumers' monthly family income was less than Rs. 50,000 The below given table (Table: 4) summaries that consumers prefer Sunday and Saturday to be the most convenient day. Survey also suggests that most convenient shopping time is evening (4:00 p.m. to 8:00 p.m.) and consumers normally spent 1 to 2 hours while visiting the organized retail stores.

Table 3 : Demographic Characteristics of Samples

Variable	Level	frequency	Percent
Age	18-24	79	40
	25-34	74	38
	35-44	31	16
	45-54	12	6
Latest Education	12th Standard	33	17
	IIT/ Diploma	13	7
	Bachelors Degree	86	44
	PG Diploma Course	7	4
	Masters Degree	55	28
Monthly Family Income	Ph. D.	5	1
	Under Rs. 50000	104	53
	Rs. 50,001 to Rs. 1,50,000	62	32
	Rs. 1,50,001 to Rs. 2,50,000	18	9
	Rs. 2,50,001 to Rs. 3,50,000	7	4
	Rs. 3,50,001 to Rs. 4,50,000	2	1
Marital Status	Rs. 4,50,001 and above	3	2
	Single	99	54
Family Structure	Married	97	50
	Nuclear	102	52
No. of Family Members	Joint	94	48
	One	4	2
	Two	5	3
	Three	15	8
	Four	55	28
	Five	43	22
No. of Children in Family	Six and more than Six	74	38
	Not any	46	24
	One	64	33
	Two	77	39
	Three	7	4
Vehicles in Family	Four or more than Four	2	1
	Four-Wheeler	15	8
	Two-Wheeler	86	44
	Both Two & Four Wheeler	90	46
Current Employment	Not any	5	3
	Full Time	140	71
	Part Time	12	6
	Retired	1	1
Present Occupation	Unemployed	43	22
	Business	39	20
	Service	103	53
	Both Business & Service	7	4
	Study	43	22
Gender	Housewife	4	2
	Male	171	87
Total	Female	25	13
		196	100

Table: 4 Convenient Shopping Day, Time and Normal Time Spent in Store			
Most Convenient Day	Most Convenient Time		Normal Time Spent in the Store
Sunday & Saturday - 87%	Evening Time (4:00 p.m. to 8:00 p.m.) - 51.5%	Afternoon Time (12:00 noon to 4:00 p.m.) - 30.1%	1 to 2 hours - 59.2%

Researchers also tried to find out whether customers would be interested in new (modern) retail stores or not. The results as per Chart-1 show that 69.4% of the respondents opined for opening the new (modern) organized retail stores. So, we conclude that there is an optimistic future for organized retailers. The survey result also reflects that 69% of the male respondents and 72% of the female respondents wanted new organized retail stores to be established in Ahmedabad. Moreover, it was also found that 78% of the young respondents (18 – 34 yrs) were in favour of organized retail stores.

Survey also revealed that 40.82% and 48.47% of the respondents' usual shopping place is organized retail store and both (organized and traditional) respectively as given in the Chart - 2. While traditional store is opted by only 10.71% of the respondents as their usual shopping place which suggests that consumers are diverting towards the organized retail stores. The survey result also pointed out that there are only 5% respondents who visits this store daily and almost 65.3% people preferred a cash payment mode.

1) Relationship between Preference of Shopping Place and Demographic Variables:

Based on the literature reviewed the following hypotheses was framed and tested by the researchers.

H1: There is no significant association between the usual shopping place and the Demographic variables (Age, Family Income, Marital Status, Gender and Present Occupation).

Demographic Variables	Chi-Square Value	Asymp. Value
Age	11.571	0.072
Family Income	8.727	0.602
Marital Status	0.332	0.857
Gender	3.177	0.204
Present Occupation	15.487	0.050

From the result it is evident that for all the demographic variables (Age, Family Income, Marital Status, Gender, Present Occupation,), the chi-square test value (Asymp. Value) is greater than 0.05. Therefore, usual shopping place and demographic variables have no significant or considerable association.

H2. There is no significant association between demographics variables and respondents opinion about requirement for new organized retail stores.

Demographics Variables	Chi-Square	Sig. Value
Age	6.867	0.333
Family Income	17.24	0.069
Marital Status	1.616	0.445
Gender	0.892	0.640
Present Occupation	6.345	0.609
Family Structure	0.248	0.883

Here, chi- square significant value for all demographic variables is very high. Hence , it could be stated that all the demographics variables are not significantly associated with the respondents opinions regarding opening of the new (modern) organized retail store.

2) Influence of In-Store Salesperson on Purchase Decisions:

H3: Consumers' purchase decision is influenced by salesperson while shopping at organized retail store.

Here, sample size is large enough, hence according to the central limit theorem the given set of data follows normality so, one sample t- Test is used to test the hypothesis.

Generally Purchase Decision Influenced By Whom	Test Value = 2 (Salesperson)					
	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
	-5.124	195	0.000	-0.342	-0.47	-.021

Here, sig. (2- tailed) value is 0.000, stating that consumers' purchase decision is not influenced by salespersons while shopping at organized retail store.

3) Importance of the Store attributes:

A seven point rating scale was applied (where 1= extremely poor to 7= excellent) to collect the opinions of the respondents. Based on the personal discussion with the industry experts it was hypothesized that more than 60% of the respondents would rate the store attributes to be good (more than 5 on the rating scale).To test the above hypothesis, non parametric Binomial test was applied as binomial test is used for dichotomous type of questions. The statistical accuracy was checked in the following manner.

H4: More than 60% Consumers perceive Product range, Store layout, Shopping convenient, Promotional schemes, Product pricing, customer service, Employee behavior, Store ambience as good (more than 5) at the organized retail store.

		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Asymp. Sig. (1-tailed)
Product Range	Group 1	<= 5	64	0.32	0.6	0.000
	Group 2	> 5	132	0.68		
Store Layout	Group 1	<= 5	107	0.54	0.6	0.071
	Group 2	> 5	89	0.46		
Convenient Shopping	Group 1	<= 5	114	0.58	0.6	0.324
	Group 2	> 5	82	0.42		
Promotional Schemes	Group 1	<= 5	118	0.60	0.6	0.508
	Group 2	> 5	78	0.40		
Product Pricing	Group 1	<= 5	122	0.62	0.6	0.286
	Group 2	> 5	74	0.38		

Customer Service	Group 1	<= 5	117	0.59	0.6	0.492
	Group 2	> 5	79	0.41		
Employee Behavior	Group 1	<= 5	133	0.67	0.6	0.014
	Group 2	> 5	63	0.33		
Store Ambience	Group 1	<= 5	120	0.61	0.6	0.393
	Group 2	> 5	76	0.39		

The test result shows that asymp.sig. value for product range is less than .01 which implies that less than 60 % of the consumer perceive product range is not good while for others Store layout, Shopping convenience, Promotional schemes, Product pricing, customer service, Employee behavior, Store ambience asymp.sig value is more than .01 which indicate that more than 60% Consumers perceive Store layout, Shopping convenience, Promotional schemes, Product pricing, customer service, Employee behavior, Store ambience as good at the organized retail store.

4) Factor Analysis: Identifying Key Store Attributes Influencing Consumers' Perceptions

The determinant of correlation matrix calculated for this analysis was $1.14E-004 > 0.00001$, which implies no case of multicollinearity among the selected variables. Moreover Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy was 0.824 stating the applicability of factor analysis. Bartlett's test of sphericity indicates that the correlation matrix of the selected variables is not identity matrix.

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.824
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2923.685
	df	561
	Sig.	0.000

Before undertaking the factor analysis, variables having less (0.5) commonalities were removed from the list. When analyzing a covariance matrix, the initial Eigen values were the same across the raw and rescaled solution and Principal Component Analysis method was employed for the Extraction of the variables. Here three variables were removed from the list of 34 variables. Interpretability of the factors was improved through rotating the factors and rotation maximizes the loading of each factor, so varimax rotation method was employed in this analysis. Here all 34 factors have been extracted in the 8 components which are mentioned below.

Table: 10 Key Retail Store Attributes Framing Consumers' Perceptions			
Factor – 1 (courteous staff members)		Factor – 2 (customers' attention)	
At this store employees are prompt serving	0.815	At this store customers get individual attention	0.819
At this store employees are courteous	0.736	At this store customers get better facilities to deposit personal belongings	0.672
At this store employees are knowledgeable	0.707	This retail store has Spotless and bright lightings	0.652
At this store employees are helpful	0.664	At this store it has convenient operating hours	0.615
At this store employees are enthusiastic	0.603		
Factor – 3 (Offers and Discounts)		Factor – 4 (comfort and elegance)	
At this store prices are with beneficial discount offers	0.758	This retail store has visually appealing shopping materials (like shopping bags, catalogs, or statements)	0.668
At this store prices are reasonable compared to the quality of products	0.653	This retail store has modern-looking equipments and fixtures	0.631
This store offers regular promotional schemes	0.617	At this store it is convenient to see price tags	0.565
At this store prices are attractive	0.615	This retail store has clean and attractive (restrooms, fitting rooms, toilets)	0.552
This store offers appealing or attractive advertisements	0.589		
Factor – 5 (proximity)		Factor – 6 (Variety)	
Location of this store is convenient	0.690	This store keeps merchandise in sufficient stock	0.720
Location of this store is proximate	0.651	This store keeps merchandise of High quality	0.670
		This store keeps merchandise of wide range (e.g. different brands, models, versions, and varieties)	0.530
Factor – 7 (speedy service)		Factor – 8 (assurance)	
This store keeps merchandise fresh and latest	0.732	At this store customers get promised services	0.979
At this store customers get fast services	0.561		

Hence, the research suggests that the following important factors could be further explored for future research.

- 1) Courteous Staff Members
- 2) Customer Attention
- 3) Offers and Discounts
- 4) Comfort and Elegance
- 5) Proximity
- 6) Variety
- 7) Speedy Service
- 8) Assurance

The above mentioned factors also state the importance of each. One could interpret that customers visiting shopping malls give utmost importance to the above mentioned parameters. Though the study was carried out in Ahmedabad city, the same could be extended to other cities and States as well to get an exact idea about consumer perceptions.

Major Implications from the Study

Given below are some of the key implications which are useful in understanding consumers by the retailers.

Many past researchers have revealed the demographics of consumers have a vital role to play in shaping consumers' perceptions. However, from the research it is inferred that usual shopping place and demographic variables have no significant or considerable association. At the same time, the findings also showed that the demographics variables are insignificantly associated with the favoring to opening of the new (modern) organized retail store.

It is also found that the most convenient shopping day is Sunday and Saturday, most convenient shopping time is evening (4:00 p.m. to 8:00 p.m.). Moreover, consumers normally spent 1 to 2 hours while visiting the organized retail stores. Hence, the

retailers must focus during these days and time of the days.

The majority (nearly 70%) of the respondents opined for opening new (modern) organized retail stores. So, there is an optimistic future for organized retailers. Moreover, it was also found that most (approximately 80%) of the young respondents (18 – 34 yrs) are in favour of organized retail stores. Therefore, to form the 'Young Shoppers' Club' is a good business strategy and the members can be offered special offers, discounts, organizing contents etc. Thus, it would help in attracting the young shoppers to visit the retail store.

Less than half (40%) of the respondents' usual shopping place is organized retail store. However, most of the consumers have visited the organized retail stores, indicating that there is great future business opportunity. Moreover, majority of people preferred a cash payment mode.

Normally, the salesperson is the one who interacts much with the shoppers in the store leading to more chances of influencing their shopping decision. However, the analysis suggested that consumers' purchase decision is not influenced by salespersons while shopping at organized retail store. Thus, the role of salesperson is important and therefore well trained and skilled sales staff is a must.

More than one sixth of the consumers perceive product range, store layout, shopping convenience, promotional schemes, product pricing, customer service, employee behavior, and store ambience as good at the organized retail store. Moreover, the research suggests that the

following important factors that one could consider that customers visiting retail store give utmost importance to the hereunder mentioned parameters. 1) Courteous Staff Members, 2) Customer Attention, 3) Offers and Discounts, 4) Comfort and Elegance, 5) Proximity, 6) Variety, 7) Speedy Service, 8) Assurance. Thus, retailers must focus on and improve on these store attributes.

Limitation of the Study and Conclusion

Along with the merits, the study also has some limitations. The data collected is from Ahmedabad and sample size is restricted to 196 only. The value of any research findings depends critically on the accuracy of the data collected. Data quality might be compromised because of number of potential errors, e.g., understanding of questions, length of questionnaire, biased samples, biased responses etc. The biasness in the findings might appear because the survey was conducted all the retail stores during the day time only. Moreover, as the survey was conducted at the exit door of the store, the samples may be biased towards the organized retail stores. In addition to this the sampling procedure is non-probability convenience sampling and thus it inherently brings all the limitations of it.

This study has shown the consumers' perceptions towards the organized retail stores which broadly helps to understand the shopper behavior. The study has revealed eight store attributes (1. Courteous Staff Members, 2. Customer Attention, 3. Offers and Discounts, 4. Comfort and Elegance, 5. Proximity, 6. Variety, 7. Speedy Service, 8. Assurance.) that mostly consumers use

to frame the store image in the retailing business. Such framed perception of certain strong attributes increases the ability of the store to attract consumers. We assume that the study would be very useful to retailers and researchers as it provides a realistic replication of the situation consumers typically encounter when they are exposed to attributes of the stores, form a perception towards the store attributes and subsequently it affects buying behavior.

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